

**Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G
experimentation facilities**

VITAL-5G Pre-Hackathon Material

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Summary

Overview

The VITAL-5G project (<https://www.vital5g.eu/>) is offering the opportunity to **test your application's performance on next generation 5G communication networks**.

This is a **completely free service**, thanks to research funding received through the European Commission.

Why Engage?

This hackathon will enable organisations to experiment with project assets and **explore the possibilities of 5G** in developing new and/or enhanced services.

You get **zero-cost access to technology experts from across Europe**, who will support you in developing and optimising your applications and services for use on 5G networks.

- This allows you to focus on understanding the benefits of 5G and showcasing the performance of your application.

Our facilities are applicable across many industrial sectors, including Transport and Logistics (T&L), Industry 4.0, IoT, automated and remote vehicle control.

- There is a choice of **three 5G testbeds** linked to trial facilities in Belgium, Romania and Greece.
- The project has developed a innovative **Experimentation Platform**, providing:
 - specialised functionality to facilitate users in readily monitoring and controlling their experiments in a flexible manner.

Goal of this Document

This document is intended to **ready those interested in attending the hackathon** by providing an overview of the project, the procedures used to engage with the project assets and an understanding of the available assets that participants can access.

Also covered are descriptions of the project trials, which provide clear examples of how the project assets are currently being used by project partners. These examples are intended to inspire other creative solutions to be proposed, developed and implemented by hackathon participants.

Organisational details

- Date and time: **June 16, 2023**, at physical locations in Belgium, Romania, Greece, Italy, and Cyprus. Online participation will also be possible.
- Venue: Venues for each location to be defined.
- Registration: Registration for the hackathon is mandatory, with limited number of participants at physical locations. There is no limit for the number online.
- **Pre-requisites: To register for the event, and to get familiar with the VITAL-5G experimentation procedure presented in this brochure.**
- Post-hackathon follow-up: showcasing of winning projects, providing feedback to organisers, potential involvement in more extensive 3rd party experimentation, and gathering feedback for future events.

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1 About VITAL-5G

1.1 General info

The strategic objective of VITAL-5G is to create an **open, virtualized and flexible experimentation facility** comprised of an intelligent virtual platform, three distributed European 5G-testbeds and associated vertical infrastructure, to enable the testing and validation of Transport & Logistics (T&L) Network Applications in real-life conditions, utilizing 5G connectivity.

Also, VITAL-5G provides **customized and virtualized** access to network and T&L infrastructure resources, enabling dynamic tailor-made service provisioning to external experimenters (i.e., 3rd parties) to validate their applications over resources otherwise unavailable to them, thus boosting confidence prior to actual service deployment. For the purpose of creating real-life 5G-enhanced T&L experimentation facilities in busy port (river and sea) and warehouse environments, VITAL-5G offers three trial sites (details presented in Section 2.2): Antwerp, Galati, and Athens, which combine 5G testbeds (5G network and virtualized and orchestrated infrastructure for deploying vertical services) and T&L infrastructure.

By delivering end-to-end latencies down to 5 ms, data rates of up to 20 Gbps, and ultra-high reliability of 99.999%, 5G is extending the capabilities of numerous industry verticals, including the T&L sector. As the T&L industry has a pivotal role in modern production and distribution systems, it is expected to leverage 5G technology to significantly increase efficiency and safety in the T&L operations, through automating and optimizing processes and resource usage. However, to be able to truly benefit from 5G, the design, the development, as well as the management, of **T&L services** need to specify and include 5G connectivity requirements, and the features that are tailored to the specific T&L use cases. To this end, we introduce the concept of **Network Applications**, as the fundamental building blocks of T&L services in 5G, which simplify the composition of complex services, abstracting the underlying complexity and bridging the knowledge gap between the vertical stakeholders, the network experts, and the application/service providers, while specifying service-level information (vertical specific) and 5G requirements (5G slices and 5G Core services). The **Network Application** concept is one of the key pillars of VITAL-5G since we envision Network Applications as the building blocks of the T&L service chains on top of 5G-enabled infrastructures.

Figure 1: Simplified schema of VITAL-5G system.

The high-level architecture of the VITAL-5G system is shown in Figure 1, and it consists of the three main segments:

1. **VITAL-5G Platform**, which is used by all VITAL-5G users, including the 3rd party experimenters, for the purpose of accessing the testbed resources, designing Network Applications and deploying them on different. It provides the various users with a unified access to all the VITAL-5G experimentation services.
2. **5G testbeds**, which deliver a 5G network infrastructure with virtual computing capabilities and SDN/NFV technologies in three different types of T&L facilities. Using the testbeds, VITAL-5G users can run their experiments and trials in realistic environments and interact with real equipment.
3. **T&L infrastructure**, which combines T&L equipment from the shipping and warehouse sectors, such as vessels in the case of Antwerp and Galati trial sites, Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) in the case of Athens trial site, onboard sensors, cameras, and 5G communication setups that enable connectivity between T&L infrastructure and Network Applications running on the 5G testbeds.

1.2 Terminology

Terminology	Definition
VITAL-5G Platform	This refers to the VITAL-5G Open Platform (or VITAL-5G Platform). It includes the VITAL-5G Portal, the VITAL-5G Catalogue, and the Management Backend systems. Vertical users and/or vertical applications access the VITAL-5G Platform to conduct experiments using the VITAL-5G toolset and Network Applications. The VITAL-5G Platform interfaces with the VITAL-5G testbeds in order to enable provisioning and testing of 5G-enabled services.
VITAL-5G Testbed	These encompass all the network elements and infrastructure necessary to enable 5G connectivity, integrated in the VITAL-5G T&L sites. In VITAL-5G these are the three 5G infrastructure installations being utilized in the use cases in Antwerp, Galati (and Bucharest) and Athens.
VITAL-5G T&L Facilities	These are also referred to as the VITAL-5G T&L Trial Facilities. They are the physical sites where the use case experiments will take place and include all the necessary hardware (sensors, actuators, gateways, vessels, AGVs, etc.) required to run the use case trials. In the VITAL-5G project, they are located at the sea port in Antwerp, the Danube river port area in Galati, and the warehouse in Athens.
VITAL-5G Portal	This is a core element of the VITAL-5G Platform and is a collection of tools/functions for Network Applications and service life cycle management (LCM). The portal allows the onboarding, instantiation, monitoring and benchmarking of Network Applications and (T&L) vertical services. Users use the VITAL-5G Portal to run experiments via a dashboard or programmable API. The intent-based Network Application descriptions from vertical actors are automatically translated into 5G slice and NFV service descriptions and lifecycle management actions. The VITAL-5G Portal contains tools for Key Performance Indicator (KPI) monitoring, analysis and diagnostic.

VITAL-5G Open Repository called VITAL-5G Catalogue	This is also called the VITAL-5G Catalogue and it is a core element of the VITAL-5G Platform that facilitates the design, onboarding, and validation of Network Applications in target environments. The VITAL-5G Catalogue is used to share and compose Network Applications for complex services and implements a Network Application and service catalogue where internal or 3rd-party software developers can onboard their own applications.
Network Application	A Network Application is a virtual application that can be deployed in a 5G infrastructure and can make use of 5G connectivity and/or 5G services (e.g., to consume network data analytics or localization information offered by the 5G Core Network) to implement its internal logic and provide its functionalities for a service consumer.
Vertical Service	The composition of one or more Network Applications, potentially designed and delivered by different software providers, giving the possibility to build complex vertical services capable of exploiting 5G mobile connectivity.

1.3 3rd party experimenters

The involvement of 3rd party experimenters that are not members of the VITAL-5G consortium (e.g., researchers, startups and companies) in the experimentation process and in the Network Application development and testing process, is a key aspect of the H2020 ICT-41 call and hence of the VITAL-5G project. VITAL-5G has the objective of engaging **different kinds of stakeholders**, mostly **SMEs**, but also **research centers** and **industries**, acting as experimenters of vertical services and developers of Network Applications.

All 3rd party experimenters will have a secure access to the VITAL-5G platform and its entire set of experimentation tools and functionalities, e.g., VITAL-5G catalogue of public Network Applications, features for onboarding and validation of new Network Applications, automated service provisioning, management and monitoring, test execution, results analysis and diagnostics. All these features have been *designed to facilitate the experimentation activities* for both internal and 3rd party users, without requiring a deep knowledge of 5G technologies. This is expected to promote **awareness of 5G capabilities for application developers** and **service providers**, providing simplified mechanisms for results analysis and the drawing of useful conclusions regarding their service and/or Network Applications when deployed in operational 5G environments.

It has to be noted that, as some of the Network Applications and equipment (e.g., vessels, sensors, etc.) provided by VITAL-5G partners can be commercially sensitive and/or require special permissions for usage, not all of the components of the trial sites will be fully available for the 3rd party experimenters, meaning that access will be restricted to a subset of hardware and software components or may require dedicated negotiations and collaboration agreements.

The main objectives of 3rd party experimentation are:

- To facilitate the availability of 5G experimental infrastructures across Europe, promoting not only their concept, but also the business offerings of 5G Testing-as-a-Service. This will lower the barriers to introduce new services and new technologies, making it more affordable for SMEs that have difficulties to build their own 5G testing infrastructure.
- To support research advancements, making them more sustainable in the long term, facilitating the efficient replication of similar initiatives in geographically distributed environments and enabling more scalable testing infrastructures, through the creation of compatible sites with unified interfaces and common experimentation methodologies that facilitate multi-site federation.

2 Hackathon material

This section provides some informative material related to the VITAL-5G components, and the three T&L trial sites that contain 5G and T&L infrastructure. The 3rd party experimenters in general, but hackathon participants in particular, will use VITAL-5G platform to onboard their newly created Network Applications and vertical services in the selected 5G testbed. Besides the general information about VITAL-5G trial sites, Section 2.2 provides insights into assets that can be used by the 3rd party experimenters. Knowing the availability of various trial components, hackathon participants might get some ideas for new use cases and vertical services that could be designed to tailor their specific business or research needs.

2.1 VITAL-5G platform

The VITAL-5G Platform, illustrated in Figure 2 has been designed to enable experimentation services for internal and external users (hackathon participants, 3rd party experimenters), with different profiles and access rights, providing functionalities and features customized for the various levels of expertise of the planned user categories. In particular, the access to the VITAL-5G experimentation services should be facilitated and simplified following a vertical-driven perspective but providing additional options for enhanced configurability, programmability and flexibility in 5G network configuration and service management.

Figure 2: VITAL-5G Functional Architecture.

The VITAL-5G Platform is structured in two main components, i.e., the VITAL-5G Portal backend and the VITAL-5G Catalogue, whose north-bound interfaces (NBI) allow the VITAL-5G users to securely access the authorized VITAL-5G services in a programmable manner, mostly via REST APIs.

On its south-bound interface (SBI), the VITAL-5G Platform interacts with the three VITAL-5G testbeds. In particular, this interface mediates the interaction with the following components of VITAL-5G testbeds:

- the management system of 5G networks (*5G Slice management and inventory*);

- the NFV MANO platforms for onboarding and provisioning/management of Network Applications and vertical services (*Orchestrator catalogue* and *Orchestrator Lifecycle Manager – LCM*);
- the monitoring platforms for collection, storage and exposure of metrics and KPIs related to 5G network, edge/cloud computing infrastructure and vertical applications or services (*Monitoring*).

The VITAL-5G Platform offers a set of services and tools that facilitate the entire experimentation process, during the different experimentation phases introduced in Annex 4.1. In particular, Table 1 provides an overview of these services and tools, mapping them to the particular experimentation phase and identifying the associated VITAL-5G macro-components (i.e., VITAL-5G testbeds or VITAL-5G Platform, with VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue).

The purpose of showing this list of services is to familiarize hackathon participants and all 3rd party experimenters with the capabilities of the VITAL-5G platform that they can explore and use during the experimentation phase. Knowing the details of each of those services is not necessary either for participation in the hackathon, or for the 3rd party experimentation.

Table 1 Experimentation services and tools offered by VITAL-5G.

Experimentation phase	VITAL-5G service or tool	Involved VITAL-5G component
Vertical Service design	Inventory of VITAL-5G testbeds, providing information on 5G network capabilities and available devices in each testbed.	VITAL-5G testbeds VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Schemas and examples for Network Application blueprints and Vertical Service blueprints, to facilitate the design and modelling of new Network Applications and services.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Catalogue of public Network Applications that can be re-used as components to build new vertical service.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Onboarding of new Network Applications, with validation of Network Application blueprint format, verification of the compatibility with the selected site, onboarding of VNF packages in the NFV orchestrator of the target testbed and functional verification of a successful instantiation in the virtual environment.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue VITAL-5G testbeds
	Onboarding of new vertical service blueprints with automated onboarding of NSDs in the NFV orchestrator of the target testbed.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue VITAL-5G testbeds
Experiment design	Schemas and examples for Experiment and Testcase blueprints, to facilitate the design and modelling of new experiments.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Onboarding of new experiment and testcase blueprints, with validation of blueprint format and verification of compatibility with the declared vertical services.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue

	Guided definition of experiment blueprints to select vertical service, network and service KPIs, evaluation criteria, test cases, and configuration parameters	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
Preparation of 5G testing environment	Guided customization and configuration of experiments, starting from their blueprints available in the VITAL-5G Catalogue.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue
Vertical Service instantiation	Automated provisioning of vertical service with instantiation and configuration of its Network Applications.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Automated configuration or selection of 5G network slices to support the vertical service.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Activation and configuration of service and network KPIs monitoring.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Validation of software licenses for Network Applications to be instantiated or scaled up.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Manual or automated lifecycle management of instantiated services and Network Applications, with closed-loop mechanisms based on predefined rules or triggers launched by AI-based diagnostics during experiment execution (e.g., for scaling or migration of Network Applications or update of network slice profiles).	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Secure interaction between Network Applications and well-defined sets of devices in T&L facilities.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Direct and secure access to instantiated Network Applications for manual re-configuration and troubleshooting.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
Experiment execution	Customization, configuration and launch of experiments.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Automated configuration and execution of test scripts.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Collection and elaboration of monitoring data: retrieval of network and computing infrastructure KPIs from the testbed infrastructure and collection of service KPIs from Network Applications components.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Visualization of monitoring data collected in near-real-time through graphs and dashboards.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal

	Direct and secure access to instantiated Network Applications for execution of test scripts and troubleshooting.	VITAL-5G testbeds
	APIs to trigger lifecycle management actions on the instantiated service and Network Applications in a programmable manner.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	APIs to retrieve monitoring data for service and network KPIs in a programmable manner.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
Vertical Service evaluation	Analysis of experiment results.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Validation of network and service KPIs.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	AI-based diagnostics for identification of bottlenecks and origin of performance degradation, with possible triggering of closed-loop re-configuration actions.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Experiment reporting.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal

Concerning Network Applications and their design, Figure 3 illustrates key components of one of the VITAL-5G Network Applications (check out Annex to see the full Catalogue), including its interaction with the hardware in the field (e.g., user equipment) via 5G network.

Figure 3 Representation of IoT Management Platform Network Application blueprint.

2.2 Trial sites

2.2.1 Antwerp trial site

In the Port of Antwerp trial site, we deploy and demonstrate **Assisted Vessel Transport** use case, which leverages **5G Standalone (SA) connectivity** and **network slicing** principles to assist vessels in the challenging environment of a port area, i.e., addressing: lack of safety in the port, too large waiting times and excessive gas consumption. To tackle these challenges, we enable **remote vessel monitoring** in a busy port area, increasing **situational awareness** in real time, and **optimizing assisted vessel navigation** through defining optimal routes and speed (see Figure 4).

In particular, a real-time **digital twin** is developed around the vessel to support the assisted vessel operation. In parallel, **real-time navigation speed optimization**, along with automated path planning and remote vessel monitoring, allow to reduce dwell times and improve operational planning of the vessel, thereby leveraging on AI/ML methodologies. The concept of **Network Applications** defined in the scope of VITAL-5G project has been used to **design and develop** these **vertical services** that support the use case. The high-bandwidth camera feeds and sensor data are sent in real-time from the vessels to the Network Applications running at the 5G edge platform, while assistance to the vessel captain is provided in real-time by sharing the navigable waypoints for an optimal route including the optimal speed. The same trial site can be leveraged by the external experimenters, i.e., the 3rd-party experimenters, which can be either involved in the use case Assisted Vessel Transport to enhance it and experiment with the existing vertical services, or create their own use cases by reusing the network infrastructure (radio, edge, and core), Network Applications, and other tools such as local monitoring platform and slice plugins.

Figure 4: Mapping the goals of the Assisted Vessel Transport use case to supported operations that can be exploited and further built upon by the 3rd-party experimenters.

In this Section, we provide further details on the 5G system components within the Antwerp trial site, as well as the Network Applications that can be reused by the 3rd party experimenters.

Concerning the Antwerp 5G-Testbed, as a core of the Antwerp trial site, it spans the usual 5G SA ecosystem components (as shown in Figure 5):

- User Equipment, i.e., a commercial vessel equipped with 5G modem, sensors, and cameras
- Radio Access Network (RAN) with three gNodeBs installed in the selected area of the Port of Antwerp
- Transport and Core network
- 5G Edge network that hosts the Network Application platform, designed and deployed to provide Network Function Virtualization (NFVI) resources for hosting and orchestrating Network Applications

tailored to Assisted Vessel Transport use case, by using Open-Source MANO (OSM)-based orchestrator and Openstack/Kubernetes.

Figure 5: High-level overview of the Antwerp trial site.

As already mentioned in this section, the overall use case is developed via creating vertical services, which are further composed by Network Applications as building blocks. Thus, here we provide a brief overview of the Network Applications that are public and, as such, can be used as building blocks for new vertical services:

- Real-Time Digital Twin (VA5)
- Remote Vessel Monitoring (VS5)
- Assisted Vessel Navigation (VS6)
- On-Board Data Collection & Interfacing for Vessel Tercofin II (VS8)

The Network Applications developed by 3rd parties can reuse those public Network Applications by interfacing with them (mainly via REST-based interfaces or pub/sub mechanisms deployed via ZeroMQ¹ technology), and thus, using them to build new vertical services, i.e., chains of Network Applications. In addition, we make one of the Network Applications fully available to the 3rd-party experimenters as open-source application whose codebase can be reused and extended to build new Network Applications:

- Navigation Speed Optimizer (VS7)

¹ <https://zeromq.org/>

In case 3rd-party experimenters are not aiming to build new vertical services and Network Applications, but to rather leverage on VITAL-5G trial sites to collect realistic data for validating their theoretical or simulation-based models, we offer several data types, which can be further extended depending on the needs and requirements from the 3rd-party experimenters. At the moment, the data types available publicly through access to some of the public Network Applications are:

- Vessel position (longitude, latitude)
- Vessel speed
- Vessel heading
- Data from on-board sensors (radar and/or LiDAR and/or camera)
- Network data collected from radio and core functions, including the network performance

Figure 6 Available assets from Antwerp trial site.

The role of the 3rd party experimenters in the Antwerp trial site depends on the background knowledge and expertise of the onboarded parties. Thus, we adjust the role based on that, and tune the support depending on whether the 3rd party belongs to T&L industry (SMEs and start-ups), or research and academia domains (research institutes, universities).

In the case of T&L industry, if 3rd party's business concerns safety and optimization of sailing operations, the following can be obtained:

- Tackling safety in sailing operations: the Network Applications for remote vessel monitoring (**VS8** and **VS5**) can be reused to remotely monitor the vessels in a busy port environment, or the digital twin one for improving the situational awareness.
- Decreasing large waiting times in sailing operations: the Network Applications for increased situational awareness (**VA5**), assisted path planning (**VS6**), and speed optimization (**VS7**), can be tested to experience and visualize how we address this issue.
- Reducing fuel consumption in port environment: the Network Applications for vessel speed optimization (**VS7**) and assisted path planning (**VS6**) can be leveraged to see how we address this issue.

On the other hand, if the 3rd party experimenter is involved in the research and development activities, or are interested in a telco-business-oriented perspective, the following activities can be performed:

- Testing the impact of 5G network on T&L or other vertical use cases: The Network Applications for assisted vessel navigation can be used on the Antwerp Network Application edge platform, and their performance over 5G SA can be tested in real-time (both real-time and historical data to be collected).

Also, the datasets with 5G slicing performance measurements are available for further analysis, or for training ML models. The 5G testbed can be exploited to create and run 3rd party applications (not necessarily T&L, but from other vertical industries) in a vertical-tailored 5G environment.

- Designing 5G-enhanced applications for other types of verticals: The 3rd party experimenters can use the design principles of applications for assisted vessel navigation as a baseline, or customize the publicly available Network Applications to create their own solution.
- Testing AI/ML solution in a real-life environment: We offer datasets collected from the vessel sensors, lidar/radar, and 5G network, to train 3rd party ML algorithms, including the opportunities to test the performance of those algorithms in a real-life environment of Port of Antwerp.

2.2.2 Galati trial site

The Romanian VITAL-5G testbed is built on an end-to-end (E2E) 5G SA network, 3GPP Release 16 compliant, which provides 5G coverage in Galati with a bi-sector gNodeB that covers Navrom ships located in the port and an additional limited area near the port, on the Danube River. Moreover, the testbed also includes the Orange 5G Lab in Bucharest, providing 3rd parties with the opportunity to perform tests and experiments in both a T&L operational facility and an indoor/outdoor lab environment.

The 5G SA network in the Romanian testbed efficiently supports both eMBB and URLLC slices. The network KPIs measured on field are in the order of 600 Mbps for downlink (DL) throughput and 100 Mbps for uplink (UL) throughput for the eMBB slice and < 3.5 ms one way delay for the latency in the URLLC slice, using a subscriber connected to one of the slices.

All the Romanian 5G testbed’s components are fully deployed and integrated covering the needs to support the main capabilities and network features keys to respond to the 5G Network Applications deployment, starting with 5G RAN, Core, Transport, Virtualization and Orchestration and extending the infrastructure to support also VITAL-5G Platform. The Romanian testbed orchestrator, based on OSMv12, is integrated with the testbed VIMs, by using an Openstack platform deployed in High-Availability (HA) mode and a Kubernetes cluster. Taking into account requirements expressed by 3rd parties, the computing infrastructure has been extended with servers featuring GPUs.

Figure 7 Mapping the goals of the Galati trial sites to supported operations that can be exploited and further built upon by the 3rd-party experimenters.

The Romanian VITAL-5G testbed components are represented in Figure 8, which also highlights the high availability deployment of transport network and virtual computing infrastructure, which guarantees seamless resiliency and application migration. The high availability and reliability tests conducted by ORO registered no 5G SA network issues for several months (more than 5 months, with at least one user permanently connected to the 5G SA network and generating traffic).

Figure 8: Romanian testbed 5G SA components and HA transport network configuration.

Available T&L Services and Network Applications in RO testbed

The design and implementation of new services from 3rd parties can be accelerated and facilitated by the use of Network Applications designed for UC2, which can be reused and combined across numerous vertical services and even across Use Cases. With the aid of assisted operations and navigation that utilise the IoT detection system and video cameras installed in Galati port and also on ships and cargoes, the vertical services that are used in UC2 as well as the corresponding Network Applications are used to ensure a safer operation in the port and to bring more security to the navigation of ships in the port of Galati. The 5G network will encompass all of this infrastructure to ensure quick transfer of data from the devices. Below a brief description of three types of vertical services that already use Network Applications developed in UC2, which can be used as examples for new 3rd party applications.

Service 1: Data-enabled assisted navigation

The service makes use of the Internet of Things sensing technology and NAVROM vessel's and Galati port's video cameras. For a specific data collection from the NAVROM vessel, **VS9** is used. **VA6** is used to classify the data stream, assign the appropriate slice (URLLC or mMTC) in accordance with the data supplied from the vessel, and provide interfaces for sending warnings and classifying events. Each incident can be quickly, clearly, and precisely categorized as either dangerous or non-threatening, as well as according to the type of dangerous occurrence. Instantaneous warnings are given to improve the vessel crew's response time.

Service 2: Accurate electronic navigation maps creation

The base of the service is determining the ideal safe distance for a ship. The accuracy of electronic navigational charts is improved by fusing velocity, heading, water, and wind speed data utilizing the distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion, and post-processing services provided by **VA2**.

Service 3: Predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes

To obtain data for on-board diagnosis and monitoring, the service utilizes **VS9** On Board Data Collection & Interfacing for Vessels. In order to reduce the influence of the human factor in risk assessment and the possibility of making poor decisions, **VA3** uses the data for remote inspection and risk assessment.

Upgrades to RO testbed

UC2 revolves around the use of sensors and ML for improving business operations in the port. A network of IP cameras, interconnected with the 5G network using a 5G gateway, has been deployed and the related video streams are available for 3rd parties. Locally the connection to the gateway is done using 5G, Wi-Fi or by a LAN Cat 6 cable, depending on the location of the camera. Some areas experience a lot of shielding due to the large metal walls and the Wi-Fi signal is unreliable; for this reason, some cameras have been connected to the 5G gateway using cables. On the video stream received from the camera located on the vessel, we implement object detection. The video stream on which the detection is applied along with all other data that is captured is sent to the 5G network using the gateway and is gathered in the testbed servers where it is logged in an InfluxDB database or streamed to a logged in user (camera video), so that they can be easily consumed by new Network Applications developed by 3rd parties. Moreover, 3rd parties can also access real-time or historical data collected from a monitoring station that measures the air quality in its proximity, as well as a wide set of engine data. The installation of additional equipment, as needed for the execution of additional 3rd party experiments, can be discussed, evaluated and negotiated on a per-experiment basis.

Figure 9 Available assets from Galati trial site.

2.2.3 Athens trial site

In the DIAKINISIS warehouse trial site, we deploy and demonstrate the “Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics)” use case, which leverages on **5G Standalone (SA) connectivity** and **network slicing** principles to demonstrate the optimization of warehousing operations through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) (VS1). The current deployment re-uses part of the 5G-EVE Athens testbed which has been upgraded Rel. 16 SA and extended at the warehouse premises. In detail, a new 5G Rel. 16 Core and a new virtualized infrastructure has been installed, interconnecting the DIA warehouse with the 5G Core through a fiber-optic cable.

This use case also supports the automated and remotely assisted operation of AGVs, using HD video streaming functionality to enable human interaction (VS2), while additional AI/ML techniques have been introduced for the post-processing of operational data in order to improve the end-to-end functionality of the warehouse ecosystem (VA1). A visual representation of the use case is depicted in Figure 10. The concept of **Network Applications** defined in the scope of VITAL-5G project has been used to **design and develop** these **vertical services** that support the use case.

Figure 10: Athens use case high-level representation.

In this case, three different Network Applications instantiate the three services as shown in Figure 11. A different combination of the Network Applications is required for the realization of each service.

Figure 11: Athens services and Network Applications.

The same trial site can be leveraged by the external experimenters, i.e., the 3rd party experimenters, which can be either involved in the use case Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics) to enhance it and experiment with the existing vertical services, or create their own use cases by reusing the network infrastructure (radio, edge, and core), Network Applications, and other tools such as local monitoring platform and slice plugins.

Figure 12: Mapping the goals of the Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics) use case to supported operations that can be exploited and further built upon by the 3rd party experimenters.

In this Section, we provide further details on the 5G system components within the Athens trial site, as well as the Network Applications that can be reused by the 3rd party experimenters.

Figure 13: High-level overview of the Athens trial site.

Concerning the Athens 5G-Testbed, as a core of the Athens trial site, it spans the usual 5G SA ecosystem components (as shown in Figure 13):

- User Equipment, i.e., an AGV, a dedicated sensor Gateway with attached environmental sensors and video camera.
- Radio Access Network (RAN) with a dedicated gNodeB with two cells installed in a selected area of the DIA warehouse.
- Transport and Core network.

- A Cloud compute resource server that hosts the Network Application platform, designed and deployed to provide Network Function Virtualization (NFVI) resources for hosting and orchestrating Network Applications tailored to Assisted Vessel Transport use case, by using Open-Source MANO (OSM)-based orchestrator and Openstack/Kubernetes.
- A testing room with a gNodeB (not shown in the picture), with similar configuration and located in the OTE premises. The partner/experimenter can choose to conduct preliminary experiments/tests in this facility before moving to the DIA warehouse.

As already mentioned in this section, the overall use case is developed via creating vertical services, which are further composed by Network Applications as building blocks. Here we provide a brief overview of the assets that are available in the Athens trial site and can be used by 3rd party experimenters.

In terms of **Network Applications**, the “Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation” (VA1) will be provided for experimentation. For example, this will enable 3rd party experimenters to create and configure a vertical agnostic and data ingestion and post-processing Network Application. This Network Application can serve as a basis for 3rd party experimenters to build their own applications by combining it with a service of their own. This can be realized mainly via REST-based interfaces.

Figure 14 Available assets from Athens trial site.

In case 3rd party experimenters are not aiming to build new vertical services and Network Applications, but to rather leverage on VITAL-5G trial sites to collect realistic **data** for validating their theoretical or simulation-based models, we offer several data types, which can be further extended depending on the needs and requirements from the 3rd-party experimenters. At the moment, the data types available in the Greek testbed are:

- Data from mounted sensors in the warehouse, mainly coming from the telemetry station (temperature, humidity, etc.) and the camera.
- Non-sensitive data coming from the warehouse and AGV operations (e.g., velocity, location, direction etc.)
- Network data collected from radio and core functions, including the network performance.

Furthermore, for the Greek node specifically, WINGS will make available a message broker, a warehouse simulator, namely a Digital Twin and a simulated warehouse environment which includes virtual AGVs, and a Fleet simulator. This way 3rd party experimenters will be able to build applications on top of the 24/7 available simulated data, avoiding the need to integrate with specific equipment (e.g., AGVs). The simulators will be deployed in a field device in DIA warehouse and will communicate over the 5G network, therefore, experimenters will be able to evaluate their application over a realistic 5G deployment.

The role of the 3rd party experimenters in the Greek trial site depends on the background knowledge and expertise of the onboarded parties. Thus, we adjust the role based on that, and tune the support depending on whether the 3rd party belongs to T&L industry (SMEs and start-ups), or research and academia domains (research institutes, universities).

3 Hackathon guidelines

Hackathon is a way of stimulating innovation and various crowdsourced solutions in an attempt to solve a specific issue. In its nature, it is a time-specific competitive or collaborative event with the end goal of building proofs of concept and viable products in an attempt to solve a previously defined problem (or to create an innovation)².

In particular, VITAL-5G is organizing this event to engage with interested experimenters and to spark the creation of new ideas for novel vertical services that can be deployed in the VITAL-5G experimentation facilities.

3.1 Objectives of the hackathon

The main objectives of this hackathon are:

- To promote **creation of novel vertical services** that boost T&L and other vertical sectors, leveraging 5G network capabilities to improve service performance.
- To create an extensive **pool of ideas** that will lead to creation of novel vertical services.
- To promote **collaboration** and engage with more 3rd party experimenters that can interact with the three T&L trial sites.
- To provide technical support and **hands-on examples** of using VITAL-5G platform and Network Applications from the VITAL-5G Catalogue.
- To promote inclusive involvement in such events, thus, **any background** of participants is very welcome.

The objectives will be achieved during a 4-hour long event, whereas the participation can be performed both online and on-site on different physical locations (more details in 3.2).

3.2 Organizational details

- **Date and time:** June 16, 2023, at physical locations in Antwerp (Belgium), Bucharest (Romania), Athens (Greece), Pisa (Italy), and Nicosia (Cyprus). The event will be hybrid, thus, online participation will be possible. The organizers will provide the link and further details in the hackathon invite.
- **Venue:** Venues for each location to be defined.
- **Registration:** Registration for the hackathon is mandatory, with the limited number of participants at physical locations. There is no limit in the number of online.
- **Pre-requisites:** To register for the event, and to get familiar with the VITAL-5G experimentation procedure presented in this brochure.
- **Team formation:** Depending on the registration, there will be a possibility to participate in teams.
- **Food and drinks:** At all physical locations, food and drinks will be provided for the participants during the hackathon. Dietary restrictions and preferences will be considered.
- **Post-hackathon follow-up:** Plan for post-hackathon follow-up activities, such as showcasing the winning projects, providing feedback to participants, involvement in 3rd party experimentation, and gathering feedback for future events.

3.3 Scope and rules of game

The hackathon will take 4 hours in total, and it will be organized following the below agenda:

- **VITAL-5G introduction (1h):** Presentation about the VITAL-5G project (general concepts and objectives, use cases and pilot sites, experimentation procedure) will be delivered by VITAL-5G partners. This presentation will summarize the main concepts presented in this brochure, and it will also include the short demo that will showcase the use of the VITAL-5G platform for the purpose of creating vertical service design and onboarding/deployment of vertical services and Network Applications.

² <https://eventornado.com/blog/how-to-organize-hackathon>

- **Brainstorming session (1h):** Generating the pool of ideas for new vertical services and Network Applications, sketching their initial design that might also include the Network Applications from the VITAL-5G Catalogue, and creating necessary diagrams that will visualize the idea. In this session, participants should think about possible valorization of their idea and impact this Network Application or vertical service might have on their or any other business.
- **Vertical service design (1h):** From the VITAL-5G experimentation procedure presented in Annex 4.1, this hackathon will cover the Vertical service design phase explained in Annex 4.1.1. The focus of this session will be on creating graphical presentation of proposed Network Application(s) and vertical services, using as an example the presentation of Network Application illustrated in Figure 3. Afterwards, the examples of Network Application blueprint, and Vertical Service blueprint, showcased in Annex, will be drafted with the help of hackathon moderators. In particular, participants will define:
 - **Task 1:** Network Application design that might include newly designed Network Application or other Applications available in the VITAL-5G catalogue (full list available in Annex). This task will concretize the **ideas generated in the brainstorming session**. The outcome of this task is the graphical presentation of Network Application(s) and vertical services.
 - **Task 2:** Specification of **mobile connectivity requirements**. This task will define the requirements towards 5G connection (uplink or downlink, or both), which will be needed for the traffic that would be exchanged between the user equipment (boat/vessel, or AGV) and Network Applications.
 - **Task 3:** Specification of **hardware dependency**. In this task, participants should define the input data that will be needed for their Network Application(s) and the end devices from which this data will be collected.
 - **Task 4 (optional):** Combination of more Network Applications to build a vertical services. This task will generate the necessary blueprints that will be needed for vertical service deployment via VITAL-5G platform.
- **Presentation of ideas & achievements, and evaluation (1h):** Each participant or group of participants will present their ideas and depending on the number of people, the time allocated to each presentation will be determined and communicated before the event. Jury will evaluate the ideas and proclaim the winning participant(s) who will receive a corresponding award.

3.4 Intellectual property

The ownership of any intellectual property developed by a participant in the context of the hackathon will remain the sole and exclusive property of the participant. The Vital-5G consortium does not claim any license or any intellectual property rights in participant's new results, except for the limited license to review the submission as part of hackathon judging.

By registering, the participant affirms that the participant is at least 18 year old and competent to enter into an agreement such as this The participant understands that the participant will be exposed to the works of others and is bound to respect whatever licenses are in effect on their Intellectual Property.

4 Annex

4.1 Experimentation procedure

The overall experimentation procedure is illustrated in Figure 15, and it consists of several phases whose roles are explained in this section. The experimentation in the hackathon will only include a subset of those phases, as explained later in this document.

Figure 15: Phases of VITAL-5G experimentation process.

The phases of a VITAL-5G experimentation process are described in the following sections.

4.1.1 Vertical Service Design

This phase has the objective of designing and implementing a vertical service (from T&L or any other vertical industry) to be experimentally validated in one of the VITAL-5G testbeds. The Service Design phase involves the following:

- Characteristic of 5G connectivity, e.g., coverage area, type of network slices supported, etc.

- Computing resources for execution of Network Applications, e.g., availability of VM-based or container-based virtualization infrastructure, dimension of resources that can be made available for a given experiment at edge and cloud nodes, added-value features like hardware acceleration or GPUs.
- Devices available in the T&L facility, e.g., IoT sensors and actuators, video cameras, AGVs, etc., and their access permissions. For example, actuators may have private access, video cameras may have restricted access, AGV may have private access but related simulators may be publicly available, etc. In some cases, specific agreements with the T&L Site Infrastructure Manager need to be put in place to obtain a controlled access to particular functionalities (in some cases under the supervision of the site personnel), especially for 3rd parties.
- Availability of public datasets, software drivers or Network Applications that can be used as baseline to develop new applications customized to operate on the given testbed.
- Opportunities for further extensions, e.g., the possibility to install new hardware, to extend the 5G radio coverage or create additional network slices.

A typical vertical service in VITAL-5G is composed of one or more Network Applications, which can be selected from the public ones available in the VITAL-5G catalogue or developed as new Network Applications to be onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform. The formal definition of a vertical service is specified through a Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB), which describes the composition and interconnectivity of the various Network Applications, the configurable service parameters, the monitoring parameters and the high-level requirements in terms of mobile connectivity. Similarly, Network Applications are defined through a Network Application Blueprint (NAB) that describes Network Applications metadata like mobile connectivity requirements, software licenses, hardware dependencies, external interfaces and related protocols, usage of 5G network services, etc. Blueprints of pre-loaded Network Applications and Vertical Services can be downloaded from the VITAL-5G catalogue and used as example for the creation of new ones. The details of Network Applications and vertical services' deployment in a virtual infrastructure are modelled through Virtual Network Function (VNF) packages and Network Service Descriptors (NSD) following the ETSI NFV standards. This approach guarantees the compatibility with the NFV orchestrators available in the three VITAL-5G testbeds, which are responsible for the instantiation of Network Applications and vertical services in the target testing environments. Both VM-based and container-based Network Applications are supported in all VITAL-5G testbeds, with the related software images that can be onboarded in the public registries and repositories of each testbed.

Once a Vertical Service and related Network Applications have been designed, implemented, packed and modelled according to the VITAL-5G blueprints format, the related packages and blueprints can be onboarded in the VITAL-5G catalogue and they become available in the VITAL-5G catalogue for the experiments or for further usage in the composition of other services. During the onboarding procedure, NSDs and VNF packages are automatically uploaded in the target testbed and they become ready for deployment.

4.1.2 Experiment design

This phase has the objective of defining an experiment for the validation of Network Applications or Vertical Services in a VITAL-5G testbed. The experiment is defined through an Experiment Blueprint (ExpB). The experiment blueprint identifies the related Vertical Service or Network Applications, the characteristics of the testing environment (e.g., network slice parameters, background traffic, etc.), the service, infrastructure and network KPIs to be monitored, their evaluation criteria (e.g., in terms of max/min thresholds), as option some test scripts for testing automation, variable and configurable parameters, etc. At the end of the Experiment Design phase, the ExpB and the related test case blueprint are onboarded in the VITAL-5G catalogue, and they become available to execute the experiments or as reference for the definition of new experiments.

4.1.3 Preparation of 5G testing environment

This phase has the objective of preparing the testing environment for the execution of an experimentation campaign and, depending on the complexity of the scenario, it may require the manual intervention of the

testbed administrators, in terms of 5G network settings or T&L facility configuration. The initial step of this phase involves the customization and configuration of the experiment and its associated Network Applications and vertical service, as well as the scheduling of the experiment execution in the target testbed. The experiment customization is defined through an Experiment Descriptor (ExpD), which is onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform. The scheduling of the experiments in dedicated time slots allows reservation of the required resources and guarantees the desired operational conditions, without unexpected interferences with the day-by-day activities in the testbeds' environments that may impact the experiment outcomes and limit the reproducibility of the results. Through the basic experiment configuration, the devices in the T&L facility and the network settings are properly configured, making the testbed ready for service provisioning and experiment execution. It should be noted that if the manual configuration of the testing environment is not required, the experimenter can immediately proceed with the following phases after the ExpD onboarding. Otherwise, an explicit notification from the testbed administrator is required to proceed.

4.1.4 Vertical Service Instantiation

This phase has the objective of provisioning the vertical service in the target testbed, triggering the instantiation of its Network Applications in the virtual infrastructure, their activation and configuration. If the Network Applications composing the vertical service are associated to restrictive software licenses (e.g., related to the number of instances that can be executed concurrently), these licenses are properly verified and validated. Depending on the dynamicity supported in the 5G testbed, the network slices dedicated to the vertical service may be instantiated on-demand during this phase, following the specification of the mobile connectivity requirements defined in the VSB. Finally, the collection of the monitoring data is properly activated and configured, according to the network, infrastructure and service KPI specified for Network Applications and vertical service. At the end of this phase, the vertical service instance is up and running in a dedicated virtual environment, with the Network Applications activated, properly configured, interconnected to the 5G network through the proper network slice and able to interact with the devices in the T&L facilities. The second release of the architecture introduces data-driven and closed loop mechanisms for automated lifecycle management actions, modelled through rules encoded in the vertical service blueprint.

4.1.5 Experiment execution

This phase has the objective of executing the experiment and collecting the monitoring data required to evaluate the performance of the service. During the experiment execution, some test scripts can be automatically configured and executed by the platform. Moreover, the user will have secure access to the various Network Application components (via Virtual Private Network – VPN), with the possibility to operate directly on their internal processes. In parallel, the mechanisms offered by the orchestrators in VITAL-5G testbeds, exposed through suitable APIs, will give the possibility to operate on the lifecycle of the vertical service, e.g., to trigger re-configuration or scaling actions even from external orchestration entities. These options are useful to evaluate how service and network KPIs vary with different deployments, configurations and dimensioning of the overall vertical services or single Network Applications. The collected monitoring data can be visualized in real-time through graphs in the web based graphical interface or consumed by external entities via APIs. The combination of APIs for monitoring and service lifecycle management gives the possibility to implement external closed-loop strategies (independently on the ones already embedded in VITAL-5G platform), directly within the Network Applications or in dedicated service orchestration logic which can be developed in 3rd party systems.

In VITAL-5G the experiment execution and the vertical service lifecycle management will be two parallel and nearly independent procedures, i.e., an experiment can be executed over a vertical service whenever the service is in instantiated mode, but the lifecycle of the service can be managed independently without any particular relationship to the status of a particular experiment. This approach enables a higher level of flexibility in the dynamic lifecycle management of the service without the boundaries imposed by experiment executions.

4.1.6 Vertical Service evaluation

This last phase has the objective of helping the experimenters in the evaluation and assessment of the vertical service performance in the 5G network. Elaborating the monitoring data and the network and service KPIs collected during the experiment execution phase, the platform analyses the results and generates experiment reports. Moreover, it performs some diagnostics evaluation to identify the potential causes of performance degradation or bottlenecks in the vertical service that may derive from networking issues at the various segments of the 5G infrastructure, poor performance of specific Network Application components or insufficient virtual resources in the computing infrastructure at the edge or core of the network.

4.2 Network Application Catalogue

Table 2 List of VITAL-5G Network Applications.

Network Application Code	Network Application Name	List of Features	Access for the 3 rd -party experimenters (PRIVATE, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED)	Type of access for the 3 rd -party experimenters
VA1	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation	IoT controller for the two-way interaction with IoT devices; MQTT/HTTP Gateway enabling the communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure; Rule engine for Decision support; Persistence service providing persistence and caching services to all other Network Application components	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
VA2	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post processing	Other functionalities related to data manipulation, fusion, and persistence; Supervised machine learning (ML)-related functionalities	Restricted	Through the delivered UI and APIs to 3rd parties: access to ML results in Map view; allow for running various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage.
VA3	Remote inspection & risk assessment	ML-related functionalities for remote inspection and risk	Restricted	Through the delivered UI and APIs to 3rd parties: access to ML results with

		assessment; Outlier detections algorithms; Ingestion of vessel engine data information from a distributed filesystem		relevant table/graph widgets; allow for running various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage. UI not originally foreseen in D2.1.
VA4	IoT Management Platform	Management of Data Buses for Data Injection: Management and triggering of custom actions for alert and event, and Customized dashboards configuration and visualization	Restricted	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3 rd parties after negotiation.
VA5	Real time digital twin	LiDAR fusion; LiDAR data filtering; Create an obstacle map of the environment of the vessel.	RESTRICTED	Access to radar and/or LiDAR raw data (from sensors); Access to obstacle map (output of the Network Application).
VA6	Data stream organization	Supports organization of data according to payload content; Supports receiving data via Pub/Sub paradigms; Supports custom processing functions (for organizing streams)	PUBLIC	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
VS1	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning	Logistics Lifecycle Management Service (Logistics LCM); AGV Task Allocation and Planning.	Restricted	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
VS2	Human-robot collaboration	HMI assist; Computational offloading	Restricted	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
VS3	AI/ML-based automated	IoT Management platform for (i) unified	Restricted	Usage of this Network Application may be

	fault detection and predictive maintenance.	collection, storage and basic processing of IoT data and (ii) control of actuators, interacting with multiple types of field buses (VA4)		granted to 3 rd parties after negotiation.
VS4	Technical data visualization.	Network based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	Restricted	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3 rd parties after negotiation.
VS5	Monitoring dashboard	Camera view of the vessel; Real-time location of the vessel on an interactive 3D map; A view that shows the result of VS7 on the dashboard and allows for the user of the dashboard to interact with VS7	Restricted	Access to the python code and JavaScript for the front end
VS6	Assisted vessel navigation	Determines a path to the destination (global planning); Finds an optimized local path (local planning)	Restricted	Access to global route map (output of global planning); Access to planned waypoints (output of the Network Application).
VS7	Navigation speed optimizer	Fully tested and integrated with VS8 to receive the geodata; Fully tested and integrated with VS5 to receive the planning data and provide the calculated optimal navigation speed; API traffic encrypted with Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificates.; Open Authorization (OAuth) v2 used for authentication,	Public	Open source

VS8	On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II	Final real-time data collection from the vessel Tercofin II; Data Proxy Server with Subscriber defined for data collection from vessel; Data Publisher for other Network Applications to subscribe and collect data retrieved from the vessel; Data manager & Data storage, and Public interface that exposes data either through a REST API, or through a pub/sub mechanism (subscribers running in other Network Applications)	Restricted	Access to GNSS data
VS9	On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel	Supports data collected from vessel: Depth sensor data, AIS data, Engine data, Air quality data, Water quality data, Video stream data	Public	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed

4.3 Network Application blueprint

Table 3 Network Application blueprint data model.

Network Application Blueprint			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
Network ApplicationBlueprintId	String	1	An identifier for the Network Application package
specLevel	ENUM (VERTICAL_SPECIFIC, VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC)	1	Determines if the Network Application is vertical specific or vertical agnostic
configurableParameters	Map<String, String>	0..1	A Map containing the id of a configuration parameter and a name as the value. These parameters can be filled in by the Experimenter at the provisioning time to customize the service instance.

Description	String	0..1	A human readable description of the Network Application package
name	String	1	The Network Application package name
version	String	1	The version of the Network Application package specification
accessLevel	ENUM (PRIVATE, RESTRICTED, PUBLIC)	1	Determines how this Network Application is shared with other stakeholders. Private Network Applications are only visible to the account of the Network Application developer, RESTRICTED shall only be available to other certain accounts, while PUBLIC ones are available for everyone to see.
useCase	String	1	The use case to which this Network Application is mapped. Used to group monitoring information and reports.
testbed	ENUM (ANTWERP, DANUBE, ATHENS)	1	The targeted VITAL-5G testbed.
applicationMetrics	ApplicationMetric	0..N	The application metrics generated by the Network Application functions.
infrastructureMetrics	InfrastructureMetric	0..N	The infrastructure metrics to be monitoring for the Network Application optimized orchestration.
atomicComponents	Component	1..N	The internal functional blocks composing the Network Application.
endpoints	Endpoint	1..N	Endpoints represent the interfaces between the different functional blocks or towards external entities.
connectivityServices	ConnectivityService	0..N	The connectivity service models a logical link which establish the logical relationships between the components of the Network Application (including the attached endpoints).
softwareLicenses	SoftwareLicense	1..N	The license terms and attached file.
required5GCoreServices	5GServiceSpec	0..N	Determines the 5G core services that the Network Application may use.
requiredEquipments	RequiredEquipment	0..N	The IoT/T&L devices used by the Network Application to work.
providedInterfaceSpec	InterfaceServiceSpec	1..N	The interfaces provided by the Network Application.
requiredInterfaceSpec	InterfaceServiceSpec	0..N	The interfaces required from other Network Applications (i.e., the consumed

			interfaces).
vnfPackagePath	String	1	The internal pointer where the VNF package is available.
testCases	TestCaseSpec	0..N	The test case specifications associated with this Network Application.

Table 4 Vertical service blueprint data model.

VerticalServiceBlueprint			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
verticalServiceBlueprintId	String	1	An identifier for the VSB.
configurableParameters	Map<String, String>	0..1 (multiple values within the map)	A Map containing the id of a configuration parameter and a name as the value. These parameters can be filled in by the Experimenter at the provisioning time to customize the service instance.
serviceParameters	Map<String, String>	1 (multiple values within the map)	A Map containing the id of a service parameter and a name as the value. These parameters can be filled in by the Experimenter at the provisioning time to determine the amount of resources required by the vertical applications, in terms of NFV-NS deployment flavour and instantiation level.
description	String	0..1	A human readable description of the VSB.
name	String	1	The VSB name.
version	String	1	The version of the VSB.
accessLevel	ENUM (PRIVATE, RESTRICTED, PUBLIC)	1	Determines how this VSB is shared with other stakeholders. PRIVATE shall be visible only to the account that onboarded the VSB, RESTRICTED shall only be available to accounts related to the same use case, while PUBLIC ones are available for everyone to see.
useCase	String	1	The use case to which this VSB is mapped. Used to group monitoring information and reports, as well as regulate the VSB access in case of restricted VSB.
testbed	ENUM (ANTWERP, DANUBE, ATHENS)	1	The target VITAL-5G testbed.
applicationMetrics	ApplicationMetric	0..N	The application metrics exposed by the

			vertical service.
infrastructureMetrics	InfrastructureMetric	0..N	The infrastructure metrics to be used by the vertical service for optimized orchestration or monitoring purposes.
atomicComponents	ServiceComponent	1..N	The functional blocks of the Vertical Service. This are mapped to the Network Applications composing the service.
endpoints	ServiceEndpoint	1..N	Service Endpoints represent the interfaces exposed by the Vertical Service. They are mapped to the external endpoints of the Network Applications.
connectivityServices	ConnectivityService	0..N	The connectivity service models logical links which establish the logical relationships between the components of the vertical service (including the endpoints attached).
Required5GcoreServices	5GserviceSpec	0..N	Determines the 5G core services to be used (if present, overrides the ones declared in the single Network Applications).
requiredEquipments	RequiredEquipments	0..N	The required devices used by the service to work. It is a subset of the required equipment dependencies of the linked Network Applications and, if present, overrides the ones declared in the single Network Applications.
nsdPath	String	1	The internal pointer where the NSD is available.